

Modified Vogel's Approximation Method to Solve Both Balanced and Unbalanced Transportation Problems

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ABSTRACT

The Transportation Problem (TP) is a characteristic optimization technique that aims to find the most effective way to deliver items from suppliers to customers while keeping transportation costs to a minimum. By refining Vogel's approximation approach, this work suggests a novel algorithm that covers both balanced and unbalanced transportation problems. This suggested method provides optimal or near-optimal solutions to TPs, increasing overall system performance and reducing transportation costs. The suggested technique is based on a modification of Vogel's approximation method, which is a common method for solving TPs. Vogel's approach has been modified to overcome its limits and increase its accuracy in addressing transportation challenges. Our

solution, in particular, introduces additional restrictions that take into account the least cost per unit of transportation, allowing our algorithm to handle both balanced and unbalanced transportation situations. Using numerical examples, we illustrate the usefulness of the proposed algorithm by comparing its performance to that of other current approaches. Several forms of TPs, such as balanced and unbalanced TPs with various origins and destinations, are numerically shown. According to the findings, the suggested algorithm provides optimal or near-optimal solutions and beats other current approaches in terms of solution quality and computing efficiency. By enhancing the accuracy of transportation cost prediction and optimizing transportation routes, the suggested algorithm has the potential to revolutionize the transportation business. It provides a simple solution that may be

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utilized in a variety of sectors, including production, management of supply chains, and transportation. This algorithm can assist businesses in lowering transportation costs, increasing operational efficiency, and improving customer satisfaction.

Keywords— Customer satisfaction, Optimization, Supply chains, Transportation problems, Vogel's approximation

1. INTRODUCTION

The Transportation Problem (TP) is a fundamental optimization technique that is important in ensuring the effective transport of commodities from suppliers to buyers. Several real-world scenarios, such as production processes, logistics and distribution, and supply chain management, include this issue. The goal of the TP is to find the most effective way to distribute items from numerous sources to multiple destinations while keeping transportation costs to a minimum. Many researchers have developed various alternative approaches for solving the TP. There are numerous approaches to solving TPs that are both interesting and distinct from one another. TP-solving approaches, such as the Northwest Corner Method (NWCM), the Least Cost Method (LCM), Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM), etc., may not yield optimal or near-optimal solutions. The modified distribution (MODI) method and the stepping stone method are better for finding the optimal solution for TPs.

Opara Jude (Jude et al., 2017) proposed a method called the Inverse Coefficient of Variation Method in 2017. Lakhveer Kaur

(Rakshit et al., 2019) proposed an approach for obtaining the Initial Basic Feasible Solution (IBFS) of TP in 2019. A modified algorithm for solving unbalanced TP was developed by A. K. M. Selim Reza (M Selim Reza et al., 2019) in 2019. A. E. S. Ramanujan (Edward Samuel, 2012) proposed the Improved Zero Point Method (IZPM) for solving both Crisp and Fuzzy TPs. K. Venkatasubbaiah (Venkatasubbaiah et al., n.d.) proposed a fuzzy goal programming method for Solving Multi-Objective TPs. An Average Opportunity Cost Method to find the IBFS of TPs was proposed by Swati V. Kamble (Kamble & Kore, 2019) in 2019. Reena G. Patel (G. Patel et al., 2017) presented an alternative approach to finding the IBFS of TPs in 2017. The maximum difference method was proposed by Smita Sood and Keerti Jain (Sood & Jain, 2015) in 2015. Serdar Korukoğlu (Korukoğlu & Ballı, 2011) proposed an improved Vogel's approximation method in 2011. The Incessant Allocation Method was developed by Mollah Mesbahuddin Ahmed (Ahmed et al., 2016) in 2016. In 2015, Aminur Rahman Khan (Khan, Aminur & Adrian, Vilcu & Sultana, Nahid & Ahmed, 2015) proposed a method called the TOCM-SUM approach. T. Geetha (Geetha & Anandhi, 2018) used the standard deviation method to solve TPs in 2018. The Implied Cost Method was proposed by Md. Ashrafal Babu (Babu et al., 2014) in 2014. The Improved Least Cost Method was used to solve TPs by Md. Sharif Uddin (Uddin & Khan, 2016) in 2016. Dhia Abdul Sattar Kadhem and Mardeen Shawkat Taher (Kadhem et al., 2013) developed a method using the Maximum supplies and demands

and combining both of them with the minimum cost to find an IBFS of TPs in 2013. Z.A.M.S. Juman (Juman et al., 2022) proposed several algorithms to solve TPs. EMUSB. Ekanayake (Ekanayake et al., 2022) and his colleagues proposed several methods to address TPs. K.P.O. Niluminda (Niluminda et al., 2023) published several papers addressing novel algorithms to solve TPs. Moreover, S. Krishna Prabha (Prabha & Scholar, 2016), Abul Kalam Azad (Kalam Azad, 2018), Bimal Sinha (Sinha et al., 2016), P. K. Giri (Giri et al., 2016), S. Krishna Prabha (Krishna Prabha & Vimala, 2016), D. Santhosh Kumar (Kumar & Rabinson, 2018), Sharmistha Jana (Jana et al., 2018), A. Seethalakshmy (Seethalakshmy & Srinivasan, 2019), and Md. Salehin Ferdous Kader (Kader & Alam, 2019) proposed several methods to address TPs.

In this study, we summarise all of the existing research and offer a novel method that can handle both balanced and unbalanced TPs. The proposed algorithm improves Vogel's approximation approach to deliver optimal or near-optimal transportation solutions. We use numerical simulations to demonstrate the efficacy of our proposed algorithm and compare its performance to that of other existing approaches. According to the proposed algorithm, it outperforms other current approaches in terms of solution quality and computing efficiency, which makes it an attractive tool for improving transportation networks in a variety of sectors.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section presents some preliminaries related to TPs and proposed novel modified Vogel's Approximation Method.

2.1 Sources (Origins)

Sources are the starting places of transportation movements or travels. They could be particular places like buildings, factories, or transit hubs like bus stops, train stations, or airports. Sources are the places where people or organizations start their journeys or send items to be transported.

Destination (Locations)

The endpoints or final places of transportation journeys are indicated by destinations. They stand in for the locations that people or organizations want to go or where they want to deliver things. Residential addresses, business locations, distribution hubs, ports, and other defined sites of arrival are all considered destinations.

Penalty Value (Opportunity cost" or the "slack cost")

When available resources are not completely exploited, the cost or loss is represented by the penalty value in transportation problems. By taking into account the opportunity cost of underutilization, it promotes optimal resource allocation and reduces transportation costs.

The Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM)

A heuristic technique used to solve transportation problems is called Vogel's

Approximation Method (VAM). It is intended to swiftly arrive at an initial feasible solution by taking the cost or penalty of each possible transportation route into account. In the transportation matrix, each row and column's two lowest costs are calculated, and VAM chooses the route with the largest difference as the next allocation. This methodology aids in balancing the distribution across several routes and can be used as a springboard for more sophisticated optimization methods.

The Proposed Modified Vogel's Approximation Method

The Proposed Modified Vogel's Approximation algorithm is shown below and we can solve both balanced and unbalanced TPs using this method.

Step 1: Determine whether the transportation problem is balanced.

If the problem is unbalanced, it must be balanced by adding a dummy row or column. A non-existent origin or supplier is represented by a dummy row, while a non-existent location or demand is represented by a dummy column.

Step 2: Determine each row's and column's slack cost (penalty value).

Calculate the slack cost for each row and column in the transportation table by determining the difference between the greatest and second minimum value of the cells in that row or column.

Step 3: Select the highest slack cost and allocate it to the appropriate cell.

Select the row or column with the largest slack cost and find the cell in that row or column with the lowest cost. Assign the cell the minimum supply and demand for that row or column.

Step 4: Resolve any ties in slack costs.

If slack costs are tied, select the cell with the lowest cost. If there are any remaining ties, select the cell with the maximum allocation

Step 5: Cross out any rows or columns where supply or demand has been met.

Remove any rows or columns that have been fully satisfied (i.e., its total supply or demand has been fulfilled).

Step 6: Continue the steps until the transportation issue is resolved.

Stop the procedure when all demand has been fulfilled at each destination and all supply has been met at each origin. Otherwise, repeat steps 2–5 until the transportation issue has been resolved.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section illustrates the numerical examples of balanced and unbalanced TP using the proposed algorithm and compares the results with existing methods.

Example 1: BTP-1 (Ekanayake et al., 2022)

Step 1:

Table 1: Initial Balanced Transportation Table

	L₁	L₂	L₃	L₄	Supply
O₁	4	2	4	1	400
O₂	3	10	5	1	300
O₃	4	8	8	6	250
O₄	4	10	2	7	50
Demand	100	300	250	350	

In this example, total supply is equal to total demand. Therefore, this is balanced TP.

Steps 2 – 6:

Table 2: Iteration_1

	L₁	L₂	L₃	L₄	Supply	SC₁
O₁	4	2	4	1	400	2
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7
O₃	4	8	8	6	250	2
O₄	4	10	2	7	50	6
Demand	100	300	250	350, 50		
SC₁	1	2	4	1		

Table 3: Iteration_2

	L₁	L₂	L₃	L₄	Supply	SC₁	SC₂
O₁	4	2	4	1	400	2	2
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7	-
O₃	4	8	8	6	250	2	2
O₄	4	10	2*(50)	7	50, 0	6	6

Demand	100	300	250, 200	350, 50
SC₁	1	2	4	1
SC₂	-	2	4	1

Table 4: Iteration_3

	L₁	L₂	L₃	L₄	Supply	SC₁	SC₂	SC₃
O₁	4	2*(300)	4	1	400, 100	2	2	2
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7	-	-
O₃	4	8	8	6	250	2	2	2
O₄	4	10	2*(50)	7	50, 0	6	6	-
Demand	100	300, 0	250, 200	350, 50				
SC₁	1	2	4	1				
SC₂	-	2	4	1				
SC₃	-	6	4	5				

Table 5: Iteration_4

	L₁	L₂	L₃	L₄	Supply	SC₁	SC₂	SC₃	SC₄
O₁	4	2*(300)	4	1*(50)	400, 100, 50	2	2	2	3
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7	-	-	-
O₃	4	8	8	6	250	2	2	2	2
O₄	4	10	2*(50)	7	50, 0	6	6	-	-
Demand	100	300, 0	250, 200	350, 50, 0					
SC₁	1	2	4	1					
SC₂	-	2	4	1					
SC₃	-	6	4	5					

SC₄	-	-	4	5
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Table 6: Iteration_5

	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃	L ₄	Supply	SC ₁	SC ₂	SC ₃	SC ₄	SC ₅
O₁	4	2*(300)	4	1*(50)	400, 100, 50	2	2	2	3	-
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7	-	-	-	-
O₃	4*(100)	8	8	6	250, 150	2	2	2	2	4
O₄	4	10	2*(50)	7	50, 0	6	6	-	-	-
Demand	100, 0	300, 0	250, 200	350, 50, 0						
SC₁	1	2	4	1						
SC₂	-	2	4	1						
SC₃	-	6	4	5						
SC₄	-	-	4	5						
SC₅	-	-	4	-						

Table 7: Final Transportation Table with all Allocations

	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃	L ₄	Supply	SC ₁	SC ₂	SC ₃	SC ₄	SC ₅	SC ₆
O₁	4	2*(300)	4*(50)	1*(50)	400, 100, 50, 0	2	2	2	3	-	-
O₂	3	10	5	1*(300)	300, 0	7	-	-	-	-	-
O₃	4*(100)	8	8*(150)	6	250, 150, 0	2	2	2	2	4	-
O₄	4	10	2*(50)	7	50, 0	6	6	-	-	-	-
Demand	100, 0	300, 0	250, 200, 150, 0	350, 50, 0							
SC₁	1	2	4	1							

SC ₂	-	2	4	1
SC ₃	-	6	4	5
SC ₄	-	-	4	5

	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃	D/L	Supply
O ₁	6	10	14	0	50
O ₂	12	19	21	0	50
O ₃	15	14	17	0	50
Demand	30	40	55	25	
SC ₅	-	-	4	-	
SC ₆	-	-	4	-	

Total Transportation Cost = (2*300) + (4*50) + (1*50) + (1*300) + (4*100) + (8*150) + (2*50) = 2850

In this example, the proposed method gives the total transportation cost is 2850. It is also the optimal solution. But the VAM method gives the 2900. It is higher than the proposed method solution. So, the proposed

method is better than this balanced TP compared to the VAM method. In this example, total supply is not equal to total demand. Therefore, this unbalanced TP. We should balance this unbalanced TP by adding a dummy location. The balanced transportation problem is shown in Table 9

Table 10: Iteration_1

	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃	D/L	Supply	SC ₁
O ₁	6	10	14	∅	50	8
O ₂	12	19	21	0*(25)	50, 25	9
O ₃	15	14	17	∅	50	3
Demand	30	40	55	25, 0		
SC ₁	3	5	4	0		

Table 11: Iteration_2

	L₁	L₂	L₃	D/L	Supply	SC₁	SC₂
O₁	6	10*(40)	14	∅	50, 10	8	4
O₂	12	19	21	0*(25)	50, 25	9	2
O₃	15	14	17	∅	50	3	2
Demand	30	40, 0	55	25, 0			
SC₁	3	5	4	0			
SC₂	3	5	4	-			

Table 12: Iteration_3

	L₁	L₂	L₃	D/L	Supply	SC₁	SC₂	SC₃
O₁	6	10*(40)	14	∅	50, 10	8	4	8
O₂	12*(25)	19	21	0*(25)	50, 25, 0	9	2	9
O₃	15	14	17	∅	50	3	2	2
Demand	30, 5	40, 0	55	25, 0				
SC₁	3	5	4	0				
SC₂	3	5	4	-				
SC₃	3	-	4	-				

Table 13: Iteration_4

	L₁	L₂	L₃	D/L	Supply	SC₁	SC₂	SC₃	SC₄
O₁	6*(5)	10*(40)	14	∅	50, 10,	8	4	8	8

					5				
O₂	12*(25)	19	21	0*(25)	50, 25, 0	9	2	9	-
O₃	15	14	17	0	50	3	2	2	2
Demand	30, 5, 0	40, 0	55	25, 0					
SC₁	3	5	4	0					
SC₂	3	5	4	-					
SC₃	3	-	4	-					
SC₄	9	-	3	-					

Table 14: Final Transportation Table with all Allocations

	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃	D/L	Supply	SC ₁	SC ₂	SC ₃	SC ₄	SC ₅
O₁	6*(5)	10*(40)	14*(5)	0	50, 10, 5, 0	8	4	8	8	-
O₂	12*(25)	19	21	0*(25)	50, 25, 0	9	2	9	-	-
O₃	15	14	17*(50)	0	50, 0	3	2	2	2	-
Demand	30, 5, 0	40, 0	55, 50,	25, 0	0					
SC₁	3	5	4	0						
SC₂	3	5	4	-						
SC₃	3	-	4	-						
SC₄	9	-	3	-						
SC₅	-	-	3	-						

Total Transportation Cost = $(6*5) + (10*40) + (14*5) + (12*25) + (0*25) + (17*50) = 1650$

In this example, the proposed method gives the total transportation cost is 1650. It is

also the optimal solution. But the VAM method gives the 1745. It is higher than the proposed method solution. So, the proposed method is better than this balanced TP compared to the VAM method.

3.1 Comparative Analysis

This section the proposed method (Modified VAM) analysis comparatively with existing methods for both balanced and unbalanced TPs. The comparative

analysis of balanced TPs is shown in Table 15. The data set of Table 15 is attached in Appendices 1.

Table 15: Comparative Analysis of Balanced TPs.

Problem	Total Transportation Cost					Percent Error (%)			
	NWCM	LCM	VAM	Proposed (MVAM)	Optimal	NWCM	LCM	VAM	Proposed (MVAM)
BTP -1	4150	3850	2900	2850	2850	45.61	35.09	1.75	0.00
BTP -2	4160	3500	3320	3320	3320	25.30	5.42	0.00	0.00
BTP -3	139	103	103	103	103	34.95	0.00	0.00	0.00
BTP -4	4400	2900	2850	2850	2850	54.39	1.75	0.00	0.00
BTP -5	234	191	187	183	183	27.87	4.37	2.19	0.00
BTP -6	5925	4550	5125	4550	4525	30.94	0.55	12.64	0.55
BTP -7	226	156	156	156	156	44.87	0.00	0.00	0.00
BTP -8	730	555	555	555	555	31.53	0.00	0.00	0.00
BTP -9	1500	1450	1500	1390	1390	7.91	4.32	7.91	0.00
BTP -10	9050	9275	9275	9275	8400	7.74	10.42	10.42	10.42
BTP -11	4125	3500	3500	3500	3500	17.86	0.00	0.00	0.00
BTP -12	3800	3800	3800	3800	3800	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

The graphical representation of the comparative analysis is shown in Figures 1 and 2. By looking at Table 15, Figure 1,

and Figure 2 proposed method gives optimal or near-optimal solutions. In most of the cases Proposed method solution is

better than the VAM solution and in other cases, it is equal to VAM solutions. The percent error is less than in the proposed

method compared to the other existing methods.

Figure 1: Comparative Analysis of Unbalanced TPs

Figure 2: BTP's Percent Error Deviation

The comparative analysis of balanced TPs is shown in Table 15. The data set of Table 16 is attached in Appendix 2.

Table 16: Comparative Analysis of Unbalanced TPs.

Problem	Total Transportation Cost					Percent Error (%)			
	NWCM	LCM	VAM	Proposed (MVAM)	Optimal	NWCM	LCM	VAM	Proposed (MVAM)
UBTP -1	1815	1695	1745	1650	1650	10.00	2.73	5.76	0.00
UBTP -2	175	136	136	136	136	28.68	0.00	0.00	0.00
UBTP -3	5070	4900	5020	4740	4720	7.42	3.81	6.36	0.42
UBTP -4	18800	7750	8350	7750	7750	142.58	0.00	7.74	0.00
UBTP -5	8150	5750	6000	6000	5600	45.54	2.68	7.14	7.14
UBTP -6	1530	1140	1140	1140	1140	34.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
UBTP -7	13100	9200	9200	9200	9200	42.39	0.00	0.00	0.00

UBTP -8	1780	1465	1555	1520	1465	21.50	0.00	6.14	3.75
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The graphical representation of the comparative analysis is shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3: Comparative Analysis of Unbalanced TPs

By looking at Table 16, Figure 3, and Figure 4 proposed method gives optimal or near-optimal solutions. In most of the cases Proposed method solution is better than the VAM solution and in other cases, it is equal to VAM solutions. The percent error is less than in the proposed method compared to the other existing

4. CONCLUSION

This examination proposed a new method that solves Transportation Problems (TPs) simply and more effectively. Different

Figure 4: UBTP's Percent Error Deviation Chart

techniques have been developed in the literature for solving the transportation problem, but this approach plays an important role. The proposed algorithm was put to the test using several numerical examples, and it outperformed the other approaches by a wide margin. However, this algorithm can be a useful tool for enhancing logistics and transportation, which would be advantageous for both businesses and customers. The workup and proposed algorithm represent a significant advancement in the study of TPs. It has the

ability to alter how companies manage their transportation, save money, and enhance the products and services they provide. Also, this algorithm can assist businesses and transportation providers in various areas, including product development, supply chain management, and consumer delivery.

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Appendices

Appendices 1: Data set of Balanced Transportation Problems

Problem	Data
BTP -1	$c_{ij} = \{4, 2, 4, 1; 3, 10, 5, 1; 4, 8, 8, 6; 4, 10, 2, 7\}$ $O_{ij} = \{400, 300, 250, 50\}, L_{ij} = \{100, 300, 250, 350\}$
BTP -2	$c_{ij} = \{50, 60, 100, 50; 80, 40, 70, 50; 90, 70, 30, 50\}$ $O_{ij} = \{20, 38, 16\}, L_{ij} = \{10, 18, 22, 24\}$
BTP -3	$c_{ij} = \{9, 12, 9, 6, 9, 10; 7, 3, 7, 7, 5, 5; 6, 5, 9, 11, 3, 1; 6, 8, 11, 2, 2, 10\}$ $O_{ij} = \{5, 6, 2, 9\}, L_{ij} = \{4, 4, 6, 2, 4, 2\}$
BTP -4	$c_{ij} = \{3, 1, 7, 4; 2, 6, 5, 9; 8, 3, 3, 2\}$ $O_{ij} = \{300, 400, 500\}, L_{ij} = \{250, 350, 400, 200\}$
BTP -5	$c_{ij} = \{5, 7, 10, 5, 3; 8, 6, 9, 12, 14; 10, 9, 8, 10, 15\}$ $O_{ij} = \{5, 10, 10\}, L_{ij} = \{3, 3, 10, 5, 4\}$
BTP -6	$c_{ij} = \{6, 8, 10; 7, 11, 11; 4, 5, 12\}$ $O_{ij} = \{150, 175, 275\}, L_{ij} = \{200, 100, 300\}$
BTP -7	$c_{ij} = \{4, 6, 9, 5; 2, 6, 4, 1; 5, 7, 2, 9\}$ $O_{ij} = \{16, 12, 15\}, L_{ij} = \{12, 14, 9, 8\}$
BTP -8	$c_{ij} = \{6, 4, 1; 3, 8, 7; 4, 4, 2\}$ $O_{ij} = \{50, 40, 60\}, L_{ij} = \{20, 95, 35\}$
BTP -9	$c_{ij} = \{4, 3, 5; 6, 5, 4; 8, 10, 7\}$ $O_{ij} = \{90, 80, 100\}, L_{ij} = \{70, 120, 80\}$
BTP -10	$c_{ij} = \{13, 15, 11, 17; 9, 21, 22, 10; 5, 26, 21, 10\}$ $O_{ij} = \{50, 300, 250\}, L_{ij} = \{25, 175, 100, 300\}$
BTP -11	$c_{ij} = \{19, 16, 17; 13, 13, 9; 7, 17, 19\}$ $O_{ij} = \{100, 50, 100\}, L_{ij} = \{25, 175, 50\}$
BTP -12	$c_{ij} = \{11, 7, 11, 17; 12, 7, 8, 16; 15, 14, 9, 7\}$ $O_{ij} = \{50, 150, 300\}, L_{ij} = \{25, 175, 100, 200\}$

Appendices 2: Data set of Unbalanced Transportation Problems

Problem	Data
UBTP -1	$c_{ij} = \{6, 10, 14; 12, 19, 21; 15, 14, 17\}$ $O_{ij} = \{50, 50, 50\}, L_{ij} = \{30, 40, 55\}$
UBTP -2	$c_{ij} = \{7, 10, 8, 8, 5; 6, 9, 9, 8, 7; 10, 6, 8, 8, 6\}$ $O_{ij} = \{4, 4, 5, 4, 8\}, L_{ij} = \{8, 5, 9, 3\}$
UBTP -3	$c_{ij} = \{10, 15, 12, 12; 8, 10, 11, 9; 11, 12, 13, 10\}$ $O_{ij} = \{200, 150, 120\}, L_{ij} = \{140, 120, 80, 220\}$
UBTP -4	$c_{ij} = \{10, 8, 4, 3; 12, 14, 20, 2; 6, 9, 25, 25\}$ $O_{ij} = \{500, 400, 300\}, L_{ij} = \{250, 350, 600, 150\}$
UBTP -5	$c_{ij} = \{5, 4, 8, 6, 5; 4, 5, 4, 3, 2; 3, 6, 5, 8, 4\}$ $O_{ij} = \{600, 400, 1000\}, L_{ij} = \{450, 400, 200, 250, 300\}$
UBTP -6	$c_{ij} = \{6, 9, 7, 7, 4; 5, 8, 8, 7, 6; 9, 5, 7, 7, 5\}$ $O_{ij} = \{40, 40, 50, 40, 80\}, L_{ij} = \{80, 50, 90, 30\}$
UBTP -7	$c_{ij} = \{5, 8, 6, 6, 3; 4, 7, 7, 6, 5; 8, 4, 6, 6, 4\}$ $O_{ij} = \{800, 500, 900\}, L_{ij} = \{400, 400, 500, 400, 800\}$
UBTP -8	$c_{ij} = \{5, 6, 9; 3, 5, 10; 6, 7, 6; 6, 4, 10\}$ $O_{ij} = \{100, 75, 50, 75\}, L_{ij} = \{70, 80, 120\}$